

TRIPLANAR CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK APPROACH FOR LIVER TUMOR SEGMENTATION

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Abstract

In this study, an automatic method based on Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network is proposed for liver tumor segmentation using Computed Tomography (CT) images. The triplanar views consist of axial, sagittal and coronal planes and these three planes are fed into the Convolutional Neural Network input streams to automatically learn discriminative features for segmenting tumor from liver CT images. The preliminary results show that Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network approach has better performance than Single-view Convolutional Neural Network approach in liver tumor segmentation.

1 INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) report, liver tumor is the second major cause of death in all cancerous disease reported worldwide, with fatalities rate of 745,000 patients in 2014 [1] and 788,000 patients in 2015 [2] respectively. Liver tumor diagnosis and surgery planning are commonly performed with Computed Tomography (CT) scan. However, there are challenges faced in liver tumor segmentation such as (i) similar intensities between liver tumor and liver tissues, (ii) small and indeterminate liver lesions which are difficult to characterize, (iii) liver tumor with different sizes and appearances (e.g. irregular shapes). Therefore, an accurate liver tumor

detection and segmentation is crucial prerequisite for liver tumor diagnosis, surgery and treatment planning.

In this work, we propose the use of multiple views including axial, sagittal and coronal images as the inputs for Convolutional Neural Network [3] for liver tumor segmentation, named as Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network. Our proposed framework utilizes different views of liver tumor CT images to extract discriminative features from the Voxel of Interest (VOI) to classify liver tumor from healthy liver region. Prior studies relating to liver tumor segmentation mostly focused on the use of Convolutional Neural Network [4]-[6] and Fully Convolutional Network (FCN) [7]. Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network method has been explored for medical image segmentation task including knee cartilage segmentation [8] and anatomical human brain segmentation [9]. In tumor related medical diagnosis, there have been efforts to apply triplanar approach for enlarged lymph nodes detection [10], lung nodule classification [11] and lung nodule segmentation [12]. To the best of our knowledge, Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network approach has not been previously employed for liver tumor segmentation in CT images. Thus, Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network is proposed for automatic liver tumor segmentation based on triplanar views in this study. The outline of this paper is as follows: In section 2, we describe the proposed framework. Section 3 presents the preliminary results obtained from the

training of Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network model.

2 PROPOSED WORK

Convolutional Neural Network is one of the deep learning models and has shown promising results in solving computer vision tasks such as image recognition, segmentation and classification in recent work [13], [14], [15]. In the proposed approach, we evaluated Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network using MICCAI 2008 Liver Tumor Grand Challenge [16] and MICCAI 2017 Liver Tumor Segmentation Challenge (LiTS) dataset [17]. The training datasets are harvested from three orthogonal views with respect to the VOI and assembled in parallel for the three streams of inputs described in section 2.1.

2.1 Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network

In Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network, we designed three streams of inputs extracted from three orthogonal views namely axial, sagittal and coronal planes aiming to detect features from different positions in liver CT image. The overall framework for Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network - Three input patches were extracted from the liver tumor CT images.

The three streams of inputs are simultaneously fed into the network, starting at convolutional layer, followed by max-pooling layer, second

convolutional layer and another max-pooling layer. The output from the three streams of Convolutional Neural Network are then combined using merge layer, ending with a fully-connected layer (dense layer) to get the final classification for the VOI. The results are validated quantitatively using evaluation measurements: Volume Overlap Error (VOE), Relative Volume Difference (RVD), Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Maximum Symmetric Surface Distance (MSSD), Sensitivity and Specificity evaluation.

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

In previous work [18], Triplanar Convolutional Neural Network approach was used to compare with Single-view (axial plane) approach to evaluate the effectiveness of additional spatial information retrieved from the three different orthogonal views. As observed from the preliminary results [18], the initial findings (5.5% accuracy improvement is observed from 50 epochs to 300 epochs in the training dataset) are promising to demonstrate the use of triplanar views in gaining additional insight to compare with existing liver tumor segmentation approaches.

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